

Newsletter 7 / 2022

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Save the date

ESiWACE2 Second Virtual Workshop on Emerging Technologies for Weather and Climate Modelling (7 October 2022)

The second workshop on Emerging Technologies for Weather and Climate Modelling will take place as a virtual event on the 7th of October 2022. The workshop, organised in the context of the ESIWACE2 project, aims to bring together scientists and industry experts working on **Machine Learning**, **Exascale hardware** and **Programming Models** to track emerging developments in areas that are relevant to the weather and climate community. In particular, for supporting future very high-resolution weather and climate models, the workshop will focus on the associated massive data processing/data analytics activities and their execution on future HPC systems.

Further information can be found at: <https://www.esiwace.eu/events/2nd-virtual-workshop-emerging-technologies>

Spread the word

Registration is open for the Training on High Performance Data Analytics and Visualisation in September 2022!

From September 6 to 9, 2022 ESIWACE2 is offering the third and final edition of its 8-hour online training course on High Performance Data Analytics (HPDA) and visualisation.

In this training course spanning four consecutive afternoons, participants will develop their expertise on data analysis and visualisation applied to climate and weather domains using [Ophidia](#) and [ParaView](#), two tools available from the open source market. The training covers topics from simple analytics tasks to workflows and applications, e.g. Python-based, and provides best practices and guidelines on dealing with massive scientific datasets on HPC architectures. **The registration is open until 2 September, 2022.** More information at the training event page: <https://www.esiwace.eu/events/hpda-vis-training-2022>

2022 CF Workshop (13-15 September 2022)

The [2022 CF Workshop](#), organised by [IS-ENES3](#), [CORDyS](#) and the [Institute of Physics of Cantabria](#), will take place on **13-15 September 2022** hosted by [IFCA](#) in **Santander (Spain)**. After 2 successful virtual editions ([2020](#) and [2021](#)), the 2022 edition is organised as a **hybrid event**, having in-person and online participants.

The **Climate and Forecast metadata conventions (CF)** are a community-developed standard designed to promote the processing and sharing of climate and forecast model and observational output data, and derived data products. The conventions define metadata that provide a definitive description of what the data in each variable represents, and

the spatial and temporal properties of the data. This enables users of data from different sources to decide which quantities are comparable, and facilitates building applications with powerful extraction, regridding, and display capabilities. The CF convention includes a standard name table, which defines strings that identify physical quantities.

Registration is required before **August 30th, 2022**.

Events that ESIWACE will participate in or has participated in

- [ESiWACE2 Workshop on Emerging Technologies for Weather and Climate Modelling](#), online, 7 October, 2022
- [Training on High Performance Data Analytics and Visualisation](#), online, 6-9 September, 2022
- [UMAP2022](#), Monterey, CA (USA), 25-29 July, 2022
- [nextGEMS Cycle 2 Hackathon](#), Vienna (AT), 28 June - 2 July, 2022
- [ICON All-staff-meeting](#), Offenbach/Heusenstamm (DE), 20-22 June, 2022
- [PASC22](#), Basel (CH) / hybrid, 27-29 June, 2022
- [Teratec Forum 2022](#), near Paris (FR), 4-15 June, 2022
- [ISC22](#), Hamburg (DE), 29 May - 2 June, 2022
- [EGU22](#), Vienna (AT) / hybrid, 23-27 May, 2022
- [7th ENES HPC Workshop](#), Barcelona (ES) / hybrid, 9-11 May, 2022

News & updates

Winner of the DYAMOND data analysis contest at UMAP 2022

ESiWACE is proud to announce the winner of the [DYAMOND data analysis contest](#) organised at the 3rd Pan-GASS Meeting, Understanding and Modeling Atmospheric Processes ([UMAP 2022](#)):

Dr. Piyush Garg from the Argonne National Laboratory, Illinois (USA).

In his Ph.D. thesis entitled "Tropical Oceanic Mesoscale Cold Pools in DYAMOND 2.5 km ICON Model" he analysed one of the global storm-resolving [DYAMOND](#) Summer experiments. [Dr. Piyush Garg](#) and his colleagues looked at 40 days of simulated cold pool climatology and compared it with a scatterometer-observed cold pool climatology. They also used random forest regression to identify the relationship between the environment and cold pools. The preprint of his paper for JAMES can be found at <https://www.essoar.org/doi/10.1002/essoar.10510600.1>. Out of 7 applications, Dr. Piyush Garg's unique analysis and its beautiful depiction in the submitted plot convinced the committee to choose him as the winner for this early career researchers contest. The prize is a "Travel Support" award financed by ESIWACE2 to attend UMAP 2022 held from 25-29 July 2022 in Monterey, CA, USA.

Congratulations!

7th ENES HPC Workshop in Barcelona (ES)

Between 9th and 11th May, IS-ENES3 organised this workshop of the European Network for Earth System modelling (ENES) in collaboration with ESIWACE2. This event, hosted by Barcelona Supercomputing Center in the Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya premises, gathered more than two hundred experts on High-Performance Computing in earth system modelling at a hybrid event (fifty on site and streaming followed by 157 unique viewers from sixteen different countries). Building on the previous ENES HPC workshops (Lecce, 2011 & 2018; Toulouse, 2013 & 2016; Hamburg, 2014 & 2020), the talks were structured around five topics (European and International HPC Landscape, Mix traditional modelling with Machine Learning, Performance, Heterogeneous architectures and Data Workflows).

More information, abstracts and recordings of the workshop are available on the [ENES website](#).

PASC22 in Basel (CH)

From 27 to 29 June, 2022, several ESIWACE colleagues attended [PASC22](#), the 2022 Platform for Advanced Scientific Computing conference, to present their work and to foster exchange.

One talk presenting ESIWACE results was [PSyclone: Enabling Performance Portability for Climate and Weather Codes](#) by Christopher M. Maynard and Rupert Ford (STFC). It introduces PSyclone, an embedded DSL within Fortran. PSyclone has been developed to improve maintainability and performance portability of climate and weather codes, as they are facing increasingly diverse and heterogeneous architectures on the HPC machines they are running on. Another ESIWACE contribution was the poster [ARM-Powered Numerical Weather Prediction: Running the ECMWF](#)

[Model on Fugaku](#) by Sam Hatfield et al, which gives an insight in his most recent work where the ECMWF model, IFS, has been ported and benchmarked on Fugakus ARM CPUs.

Furthermore, ESIWACE members organised three minisymposia on behalf of either ESIWACE2 or their home institutions:

- [MS2A - Leveraging Data Lakes to Manage and Process Scientific Data](#)
- [MS2C - Nexus of AI and HPC for Weather, Climate, and Earth System Modelling](#)
- [MS3C - ICON-Next: Current Developments in Rewriting the ICOSahedral Non-hydrostatic \(ICON\) Model for Emerging Architectures](#)

These minisymposia gathered experts of one field from different institutions and therefore allowed intense and fruitful discussions.

Europa Village @ Teratec Forum near Paris (FR)

ESIWACE was present, as every year, at the Europa Village of the Teratec Forum, which took place in Palaiseau near Paris on 14 and 15 June, 2022. This is a reference event in France and Europe that brings together top international experts in High Performance Computing, Simulation and Big Data. It was a big success with a lot of people visiting the Europa Village, with many discussions on European projects such as EPI, IO-SEA, RED-SEA, EUPEX, etc. More information is available on the [Teratec website](#).

ISC'22 in Hamburg (DE)

ISC High Performance 2022, a major event for High Performance Computing, Machine Learning and Data Analytics and themed **#TransformingTheFuture** this year, took place as an on-site event in Hamburg, Germany from 29 May till 2 June, 2022. A number of ESIWACE partner institutions were involved in activities at ISC'22, e.g. with conference exhibition booths, as listed [here](#).

At exhibition booth no. H801, DKRZ staff provided information on DKRZ's new supercomputer "Levante", and on a large 4k touch screen visitors were able to get a glimpse of current, high-resolution global climate visualisations.

Moreover, visitors had the chance to sign up for and take a guided tour to the new system at the DKRZ premises. For ESiWACE, Erwan Raffin (Atos), Ben van Werkhoven (NLeSC), David Guibert (Atos) and Julia Duras (DKRZ) had contributed a [project poster](#) on the ESiWACE2 [HPC user-service "Model Refactoring and Porting"](#), which was presented by Erwan Raffin during the poster session on Tuesday, May 31, 2022.

Snapshots

Atos Bull

Atos has almost finished the OGSTM and BLOM HPC user-service "Model Refactoring and Porting" projects (Service 1). For OGSTM, two main sections have been ported to GPU using OpenACC. This represents an important first step toward a global GPU porting of the code. Regarding BLOM, the hybrid MPI/OpenMP parallelisation has been deeply profiled and analysed.

BSC

BSC is finishing the [Autosubmit](#) 4.0 version. A beta version is now under test at BSC premises. This major version upgrade will add support for Python3, YAML configuration files (improving the usability of the experiment setup phase) and multiple improvements to support workflows on the pre-exascale machines and future projects.

CERFACS

CERFACS has produced deliverable [D6.2 "Report on the different trainings"](#) that details the trainings offered by ESiWACE2 WP6 on pre-exascale HPC software engineering, methods and tools applied to the domain of weather and climate modelling: I/O, DSL, C++, code coupling, data analytics and containerisation.

CMCC

CMCC contributed to D5.2 on the implementation of the ESDM PAV analytical kernels describing the Ophidia extensions and the related kernels to support in-flight analytics via the ESDM streaming API. A preliminary evaluation has been started to understand the performance of the developed solutions. Moreover, CMCC is coordinating the

organisation of the Second Workshop on Emerging Technologies for Weather and Climate Modelling, which will be held online in October.

DKRZ

While continuously standardising the received DYAMOND Winter simulation data, we include them in our intake-esm catalogue and improve their documentation on <https://easy.gems.dkrz.de/DYAMOND/index.html> to simplify their analysis and to ease comparisons. Up to now, we have post-processed nearly 9 out of 11 models with various experiments. In strong cooperation with our neighbour project [nextGEMS](#) we provide tutorials, scripts and hints on post-process storm-resolving earth system model simulations at <https://easy.gems.dkrz.de/Processing/index.html>. We have accomplished a first prototype of the in-situ visualisation tool YAVIZ (Yet Another Visualization interface). YAVIZ connects the coupler YAC to Paraview's Catalyst interface, which allows in-situ 3D visualisations of the data to be generated.

As part of the DKRZ booth and by having contributed to a poster on ESIWACE services, we presented ESIWACE at the ISC High Performance conference in Hamburg. Last but not least we have spread the word about ESIWACE contributions to various conferences and workshops.

ETH Zürich / CSCS

CSCS is happy to announce that the containerisation of COSMO for the M48 deliverable D2.9 of WP2 (now in February 2023) has made excellent progress. This contribution has come from an unexpected source, namely ETH Zürich / C2SM, which is not specifically funded from ESIWACE2, as well as MeteoSwiss (which does receive funding). We thank C2SM sincerely for their contributions to WP2.

As a prelude to D2.9, the containerised models to be delivered will be LFRic (prepared by UREAD, among others), COSMO (C2SM/MCH) and ICON (C2SM/CSCS).

SMHI

The EC-Earth 4 model has undergone a round of major component upgrades and comes now with OpenIFS 43r3v2, NEMO4.2 and the latest XIOS version. This activity brings EC-Earth users a number of new features and performance improvements for this post-CMIP6 version and is to a large extent a direct outcome of the ESIWACE2 project: A number of component upgrades bring features and improvements that were developed or supported by ESIWACE work packages (e.g. OASIS3-MCT 5.0, NEMO4.2 and XIOS) and provide them to climate researchers. On the other hand the new EC-Earth version feeds back into work package WP1 of ESIWACE by providing a new baseline version for the testing on pre-exascale machines.

UKRI/STFC

STFC are continuing work on the application of PSyclone to NEMO with OpenACC GPU, OpenMP GPU and OpenMP CPU versions in development. STFC and MeteoSwiss are also working on PSyclone 2 Dawn interoperability via the SIR intermediate representation.

Recent ESIWACE2-related Publications

Irrmann, G., Masson, S., Debreu, L., Guibert, D., and Raffin, E.: Optimizations of Multiscale Simulation with AGRIF, towards Exascale Applications, EGU General Assembly 2022, Vienna, Austria, 23–27 May 2022, EGU22-12292, <https://doi.org/10.5194/egusphere-egu22-12292>, 2022.

Streffing, J., Yepes-Arbós, X., C. Acosta, M., and Serradell, K.: Approach to make an I/O server performance-portable across different platforms: OpenIFS-XIOS integration as a case study, EGU General Assembly 2022, Vienna, Austria, 23–27 May 2022, EGU22-8094, <https://doi.org/10.5194/egusphere-egu22-8094>, 2022.

Yepes-Arbós, X., Di, S., Serradell, K., Cappello, F., and C. Acosta, M.: Exploring the SZ lossy compressor use for the XIOS I/O server, EGU General Assembly 2022, Vienna, Austria, 23–27 May 2022, EGU22-9153, <https://doi.org/10.5194/egusphere-egu22-9153>, 2022.

News from the neighbors

NextGEMS Cycle 2 Hackathon in Vienna successfully completed

From Tuesday, 28 June till Saturday, 2 July, 2022 nearly 100 researchers and programmers got together in Vienna for a joint hacking experience: exploring, analysing and developing workflows using the [nextGEMS Cycle 2 simulation data sets](#). Hosted by Prof. Aiko Voigt, professor of climate science at the University of Vienna, the Cycle 2 hackathon of our partner project [nextGEMS](#) comprised five days full of inspiring input, exchange, collaboration and output such as data handling workflows, post-processed data, plots and visualisations.

Before they started with the actual hacking, the hackathon participants received a thorough introduction to the latest storm-resolving simulations with the nextGEMS models ICON and IFS. Guided by a data support team among them Florian Ziemen (DKRZ) and scientific programmers from the modelling teams, participants learned the ropes of handling the model output: Interactive and batch processing on [DKRZ's new supercomputer Levante](#) using the intake-esm catalogue, the command-line tool Climate Data Operators (CDO), and Python in Jupyter notebooks. The actual hacking on days three to five targeted the four storm-related nextGEMS research themes and an additional renewable energy challenge problem.

ESiWACE has supported the hackathon with compute time resources provided via the DYAMOND initiative, data handling techniques and funding for a pleasant hackathon location.

Read more on nextGEMS and the Cycle 2 hackathon at:

<https://nextgems-h2020.eu/cycle-2-hackathon/>

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